

success story

EIFFEL becomes a GEO Knowledge Hub provider delivering 8 knowledge packages

Demonstrating how European R&D projects can contribute to the GKH under the EuroGEO flag.

EIFFEL is a GEO-related project by design, as reflected in the Topic itself as well as the Grant Agreement, where KPI of 3 was the mandate regarding creation of GKH knowledge packages. As partner, the National Observatory of Athens which hosts the Greek GEO Office, i.e. a national coordination mechanism in GEO-nomenclature, provided guidance on all things related to the GEO ecosystem while only a few partners had a previous involvement with GEO. This guidance was necessary to meaningfully introduce the partners to the GEO ecosystem and the GKH itself. The end result is that 8 EIFFEL knowledge packages will comprise the project's contribution to the GKH.

This diverse contribution, ranging from water management and nature based solutions to urban GHG mitigation and agricultural/forest practices as well as ontologies, would not have been possible without the active support and collaboration with the GEO Secretariat, culminating in the March 2024 webinar which might serve as a reference point for other projects. It is important to note that, apart from e-shape, EIFFEL is the first Horizon project to systematically contribute to the GKH under the EuroGEO tag. These 8 packages have been tagged with the relevant GEO Work Programme activity: including GEOGLAM, GEOGLOWS, GWIS, GFOI, GEO-VENER, EO4SDG and DATA-WG. However, a long-term working relationship has yet to be established but the GKH entries will commence this process which entails matters of GEO governance and action on the part of the knowledge providers, post-EIFFEL, such as the creation of webinars with GEO Secretariat support.

The bountiful contribution should not obscure the critical fact that the added value of contributing to the GEO Knowledge Hub was not immediately evident to the EIFFEL providers. While benefits were underlined by the Greek GEO Office and the GEO Secretariat, this hesitancy is likely to be more pronounced in GEO-agnostic R&D projects that employ Earth Observation and could potentially contribute to GEO under the EuroGEO flag. This issue goes well beyond the EIFFEL project and necessitates further discussion in the EuroGEO community regarding the whether/why/how of the said contribution. Hopefully, the EIFFEL experience will contribute towards this.

Useful links:

www.eiffel4climate.eu

<https://www.eiffel4climate.eu/index.php/pilots>

 @eiffel4climate

 eiffel4climate project

